

Pathways to Interdisciplinary and Transdisciplinary Research: the SHAPE-ID Toolkit

Find tools and resources to make informed decisions about interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary research with the Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences, the Sciences, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics, and societal partners.

Evaluate inter- and transdisciplinary research

Abstract

Disciplines help to organise knowledge for quality assessment purposes and are the cornerstone of academic peer review and recognition. How do we judge what “good” research is if it is outside of our immediate sphere of expertise?

This publication compiles resources collected as part of the SHAPE-ID project to support researchers, funders/policymakers, research organisations and societal partners in evaluating inter- and transdisciplinary research.

Compiled by

Isabel Fletcher and Catherine Lyall

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SHAPE-ID consortium members

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Online source – SHAPE-ID Toolkit

This publication is an extract of the SHAPE-ID Toolkit. For a general overview, visit: [10.5281/zenodo.4743703](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4743703).

The Toolkit provides tools and resources to make informed decisions about interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary research with the Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences, the Sciences, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics, and societal partners.

Contributors & Co-producers

The SHAPE-ID resource collection series is an artefact of collective wisdom. Some resources were generated by the SHAPE-ID team, but many were already available online and the toolkit acts as a gateway to locate them. The SHAPE-ID collection series is based on discussions with and inputs from the SHAPE-ID consortium members, namely Anna Buchner, Maureen Burgess, Bianca Vienni Baptista, Caitriona Curtis, Isabel Fletcher, Giorgia Galvini, Catherine Lyall, Maciej Maryl, Jane Ohlmeyer, Christian Pohl, Andrea Ricci, Carlo Sessa, Jack Spaapen, Sibylle Studer, Doireann Wallace, Piotr Wcislik, Keisha Taylor Wesselink, Declan Whelan-Curtin.

SHAPE-ID resource collection series

- Understand inter- and transdisciplinary research: [10.5281/zenodo.4743671](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4743671)
- Develop collaborative conditions: [10.5281/zenodo.4743673](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4743673)
- Co-create a research project: [10.5281/zenodo.4743675](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4743675)
- Fund collaborative research: [10.5281/zenodo.4743677](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4743677)
- Evaluate inter- and transdisciplinary research: [10.5281/zenodo.4743679](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4743679)
- Disseminate inter- and transdisciplinary research findings: [10.5281/zenodo.4743683](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4743683)
- Improve inter- and transdisciplinary research skills: [10.5281/zenodo.4743685](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4743685)
- Support collaborative researchers: [10.5281/zenodo.4743687](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4743687)
- Develop a career in inter- and transdisciplinary research: [10.5281/zenodo.4743689](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4743689)

Evaluate Inter- and Transdisciplinary Research

Disciplines help to organise knowledge for quality assessment purposes and are the cornerstone of academic peer review and recognition. How do we judge what “good” research is if it is outside of our immediate sphere of expertise?

Resource highlights

- ▶ SHAPE-ID Reflective tool for reviewers of inter- or transdisciplinary research proposals: [10.5281/zenodo.4743695](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4743695)
- ▶ Guide to SHAPE-ID toolkit resources for evaluation: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5116027>
- ▶ SHAPE-ID Top Ten Tips on evaluating inter- and transdisciplinary research: [10.5281/zenodo.4743693](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4743693)

Subtopics

Find out about good practice in ID/TD evaluation

Appoint ID/TD evaluators

Assess the feasibility and impact of an ID/TD approach in research proposals

Resources per subtopics

Find out about good practice in ID/TD evaluation [^](#)

Comprehensive reviews of good practice in inter- and transdisciplinary evaluation are given in Christian Pohl and co-authors' 2011 article *Questions to evaluate inter- and transdisciplinary research proposals*.

[READ PDF](#)

And in Catherine Lyall and Emma King's report on international good practice in interdisciplinary peer review.

[READ PDF](#)

A similar review is provided with Veronica Strang and Tom McLeish's overview from the perspective of an Institute of Advanced Study.

[READ PDF](#)

Shorter summaries are provided in this guide on reviewing interdisciplinary research proposals.

[READ PDF](#)

And this guide to evaluating interdisciplinary research.

[READ PDF](#)

In this 5 min video clip, Emily Woollen and Catherine Lyall from the University of Edinburgh discuss the evaluation of interdisciplinary research and how it might be improved.

[WATCH VIDEO](#)

The Belmont Foundation offers resources on evaluating transdisciplinary approaches and developing research metrics for transdisciplinary research including approaches and indicators for evaluation (see pages 9–10).

[READ PDF](#)

Further advice on evaluation and recommendations for funders designing review processes are provided in this briefing note.

[READ PDF](#)

The theme of appropriate research metrics for interdisciplinarity is also explored in this i2Insights blog.

[VISIT SITE](#)

SHAPE-ID partners Christian Pohl and Isabel Fletcher provide their Top Ten Tips for evaluating inter- and transdisciplinary research.

[READ PDF](#)

Appoint ID/TD evaluators [▲](#)

There is general agreement that interdisciplinary proposals will require a higher number of reviewers. The selection of evaluators and the design of review processes is addressed in Catherine Lyall and Emma King's 2013 report on the topic.

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This Open Access chapter deals with evaluating interdisciplinary proposals, programmes and publications and provides several Key Advice summaries such as Key Advice 7.3 Tips for effective interdisciplinary review panels.

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Assess the feasibility and impact of an ID/TD approach in research proposals [▲](#)

In addition to the good practice guidelines (see **Find out about good practice in ID/TD evaluation**), several commentators have suggested sets of questions that reviewers might adopt to probe quality indicators. For further details and full citations see Lyall and King (2013).

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This SHAPE-ID Reflective Tool for evaluators of inter- and transdisciplinary research proposals will guide reviewers in assessing the feasibility and quality of research proposals. It provides guidance on whether the proposed research demands an inter- or transdisciplinary approach and is truly integrative in nature. This means, for example, searching for evidence of a joint research question, joint theory formation and shared methods, data and materials.

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SHAPE-ID has produced this guide reflecting on the need for new methods of evaluating inter- and transdisciplinary research, with a list of further resources.

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